

NON-VERBAL GREETINGS IN DIFFERENT CULTURE

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Abstract: This article deals with various types of non-verbal greetings that can be seen in all languages. They are linguistic routines that form part of the repertoire of politeness and serve as means for opening conversations appropriately, establishing, maintaining and negotiating social relationships. There are some types of greetings and they can differentiate from one another due to their cultures that denote various meaning. In the article, the culture of greeting in Japanese, Chinese, Karakalpak and Malays are represented and here, you may learn the sorts of greetings in different cultures.

Key words: non-verbal greeting, bowing, bowing and handshaking, handshake, rubbing hands.

Introduction

In our life, we mostly use verbal language to communicate with people in our society and it supposed to be main means of communication. There are a number of languages and cultures in the world that can be differentiate from one another. When it comes to greetings, we can easily notice the difference since the language pronounced verbally. For instance:

In Japanese: Kon'nichiwa (こんにちは)

In Chinese: Nǐ hǎo (你好)

In Karakalpak: Assalauma aleykum.

In English: Hello.

In Malay: Salaam

When we greet people, non-verbal greeting can be used as well by acting with head, hand and body. Comparing some nation's culture of greetings, we can indicate some differences and similarities.

Methodology

We can see that in a non-conflicting culture with public space being managed empathically, that is, the one which is based on peacebuilding gestures, greeting gestures occupy a central position in the human symbolic capital, owing to its manual interpersonal communicative power. [1;135-142]. Gestures play highly essential role in all aspects of interpersonal communication.

Thanks to them human communication agents are able to communicate with each other and provide many messages which convey verbal and also nonverbal meanings. Even though there exist many different types of gestures, greeting ones are perceived as an essential and crucial part of everyday life. They are highly important in interpersonal communication used in different communicative niches. Greeting gestures are vital as a presenter of a first image creator. First impressions are very significant for a variety of reasons. On the one hand greeting gestures are culturally diverse, but on the other hand it is important for people to be aware of this in order to communicate positively and without misunderstandings. One can distinguish many forms of greeting gestures depending on culture. Greetings are widely used in people's daily life. However, due to the differences in geographical location, history, culture and cultural background, greetings are also very different. Moreover, greeting can be described as the exchange of expressions, pleasantries or good wishes between two people interacting for the purpose of fulfilling social obligations, or for the establishment of interpersonal relationships. It takes place at the opening of an interaction or as a marker of its closing. It can be regarded as a necessary opening to every new encounter. Consequently, in this article we tied to illustrate kinds of greetings in different cultures in the following paragraphs.

Discussion

Bowing as a greeting gesture

Greeting gesture is a Japanese bowing which is considered to be a form of loyalty, courtesy, politeness and personal responsibility. When it comes to meetings and greeting, Japanese people bow. The bow as a form of greeting gesture is highly regarded in order to show respect and is very much appreciated by the Japanese people. Ahmad pointed out that for Japanese society, in most of the situations, bowing would be the only polite gesture to make, since this culture belongs to noncontact cultures and any body contact is rather perceived as taboo, and treated as an unwanted behavior. What is also worth mentioning is that, Japanese bowing is gender based. There exist different forms of greetings reserved for men and women. As Ahmad observed men and women bow differently. Men usually keep their hands at their sides, while women put their hands together along their thighs. Additionally, people who are of lower status bow longer and lower. According to Ahmad Japanese greetings gesture consist of three degrees of bowing:

- 15 degree bow – it is the most informal bow and is used for casual greetings. It is obligatory on the part of a greeter to bow before the greete. In addition, it is highly impolite not to return a bow if a greeter bows to a greete.
- 30 degree bow – it is common when greeting customers or simply when thanking someone. It can also be observed in semi-formal business communicative situations.
- 45 degree bow – it is the most formal type of bow. It signifies deep gratitude, a respectful greeting, a formal apology, asking for favors, etc [2; 48-122].

Bowing and handshaking as a greeting gesture

Another greeting gesture can be observed in China. While meeting and greeting, Chinese may nod or bow and add handshakes which have become increasingly common. As Ahmad observed it is due to the influence from the Western culture and thus handshake is widely used in China. However, a nod of the head or slight bow will be sufficient. What is more, in Western cultures while greeting, there also appears a smile, Chinese people mostly do not smile during a greeting gesture. Chinese people

have the attitude of keeping their feelings inside them than showing emotions openly and publicly. What is more, as Ahmad pointed out their handshake is rather light and sometimes might be prolonged. In Chinese culture men and women may shake hands, however, woman is obliged to extend her hand first, while men should wait to shake hands. While meeting with elderly people, it is a senior who begins greetings. What is more, it is required to greet the oldest, most senior person before others. Ahmad added that the handshake should be gentler and definitely accompanied by a slight nod. Furthermore, it can be observed that the vast majority of older Chinese lower their eyes while greeting in order to show a respect. There also exists a norm that while greeting friends, one should say “how do you do”, nod head or shake hands. This form of greeting is performed between the same genders and the opposite ones as well. A handshake may be prolonged than normal one in Western cultures and this signifies a gesture of respect [2; 64-65].

Handshake as a greeting gesture

Among many greeting gestures people perform every day, handshake is the most common one. Handshake is said to be one of the most common and most taken-for-granted gesture which is used by human beings while meeting each other. Nevertheless, it may differ across the world. In various cultures handshakes are not performed in the same way. The free hands have made it possible for humans to develop and perform an important hand-touching and culture-determined ritual, the handshake, in the procedure of human-to-human encounter [1;135-142].

According to Merriam Webster’s Learner’s Dictionary, handshake is the act of grasping someone’s right hand with your right hand and moving it up and down. What is more, the handshake has the general meaning of equality in the sense of mutual denials of deference to self and mutual expressions of respect for the other [3; 251]. From nonverbal perspective, handshake is an act of touch and greeting that is performed between two persons. Therefore, by observing handshake interactions, many social and interpersonal messages can be discerned. Nevertheless, handshake has a communicative function and replaces verbal expression such as “hello” [4;26].

According to Schroeder [5; 743-768], handshakes are seen as ritualistic behavior and are considered a “greeting ritual” because they are commonly used at the start of social interactions. In addition, it is important to mention that handshake is often the first behavioral act which occurs when people meet and through handshake the information is conveyed [6;1140]. Moreover, by this non-violent attitude, “the handshake is used by communicators to open up an agenda, this is, it opens up a common ground for peaceful exchange of information and for making a familiar space which involves the handshake as a strong signal sent to the other human being(s) as regards the readiness both to cooperate and receive reciprocity” [1; 140]. The significance of a handshake is not circumscribed to a specific national group. It is rather perceived worldwide as an interpersonal greeting gesture. However, it may be found across the globe, but there can be distinguished many nuances within gesture which may have significant impact on the meaning. Thus, there may appear different misunderstandings, hence it may cause numerous different meanings attached to the handshake as well as different styles of performing it [7; 60-76]. As Ahmad observed firm, hearty handshake is a tradition in European countries. In addition, this grip is not so tight, and what is more, there is little or no shaking action. Nevertheless, the handshake in greeting is seen as a vital gesture and may imply various interpersonal interactions.

Karakalpak culture

In Karakalpak language, the culture of greeting can be performed in various forms like by word, sentence or in the form of text. The verbal greeting such as «Ассалаўма алейкум», «Ўэлийкум эссалам», «Сэлем», «Сэлем бердик», «Саламатсыз ба» are supposed to be common daily greetings of this nation and considered to be verbal form of greetings since language units are used verbally. Besides that, greetings can be performed non-verbally by the action of the body. Karakalpak people use their hands to handshake each other. The Karakalpak greeting is utilized hands with following words as “Assalawma áleykum”, but in some places “Sálem. Salem berdik. How are you?” greetings in terms of age, gender. The phrase “Sélem berdik” is used in the more colloquial and artistic style of the Karakalpak language. When sitting at a party or

anywhere, the last man or woman to come here, the people who came first (if they are acquaintances) by shaking hands, which is called "taking away". That is, it is often taken from the hands of older people. Hello, how are you? Is your parents or children good? Bala-shaǵań amanba? How is your jobs or studies? Are the kids growing up? etc. in the form of a question. If in the circle folks are younger, they will stand up and greet the visitors. If the hosts or guests are older than these younger individuals [8].

As we mentioned above bowing non-verbal greeting is used in Chinese culture, but bowing can be used in Karakalpak culture as well. Bowing is not supposed to be daily greeting. It can be performed at the wedding when bride comes to fiancé's home. According to the tradition of Karakalpak, the bride should bow before entering the fiancé's house. Here, bowing denotes greeting her father-in-law, mother-in-law and other fiancé's relatives [9].

Rubbing hands as a greeting gesture

Greeting gestures are very important part of social life. Malays greet each other with bringing palms together (as if to shake hands) and placing it between one's own [2; 67]. In addition, it is important to mention that Malays greeting gesture is called "Hello/salaam". People extend both hands and at the same time grasp their hands (like a double handshake). However, in Malaysia greeting forms vary depending on the age, ethnicity and situation. For example, it is a norm that Malay women do not rub hands with men, unless women extend their hands first. Women may instead bow and place her hand on her heart as showing respect. Nevertheless, women can rub hands with women. What is more, after rubbing hands it is possible that they bring their hands to their hearts. This is a symbol of greeting showing the highest level of respect to other person.

Conclusion

To sum up, we can show that different greetings gestures across cultures are perceived as an important element of interpersonal communication and most of them do evoke the feeling of empathy and thus may build peaceful communication between communicators. Greeting gestures are extremely important gestures in human culture.

Their communicative power and significance lie in building positive potential, for they directly serve to remove tensions between communicators that may occur within one but also across different cultures. The empathic and peace building value of all presented greeting gestures ought to be cherished as a central gestural interaction engine which human beings developed in the course of human evolution.

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